

Notas breves

First record of *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2007 (Gastropoda, Phasianellidae) in Spain

Primera cita de *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2007 (Gastropoda, Phasianellidae) en España

Bruno AMATI* & Marco OLIVERIO**

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INTRODUCTION

The phasianellid subfamily Tricolinae Woodring, 1928 includes the single genus *Tricolia* Risso, 1826, with 32 recognised Recent species (MOLLUSCABASE, 2019). The genus has the largest diversity in South Africa (12 species: NANGAMBI & HERBERT, 2006; 2008; NANGAMBI, 2010; HERBERT, 2015), and in the eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean (12 species: TALAVERA, 1978; GOFAS, 1982; 1986; 1993; VAN AARTSEN ET AL., 1984; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011), whereas only 8 species are known in the Indian and Pacific Oceans (e.g.: ROBERTSON, 1958, 1985). The ten recognised species in the Mediterranean have been recently excellently figured by SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI (2011): *Tricolia pullus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Tricolia tenuis* (Michaud, 1829), *Tricolia speciosa* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1824), *Tricolia nordsiecki* (Talavera, 1978), *Tricolia miniata* (Monterosato, 1884), *Tricolia*

punctura Gofas, 1993, *Tricolia tingitana* Gofas, 1982, *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2007, *Tricolia entomocheila* Gofas, 1993, *Tricolia deschampsii* Gofas, 1993. Of those, eight are known from the Mediterranean Spanish waters (Gofas et al., 2017), with the exception of *T. punctura* and *T. landinii*.

The most recently described species, *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2007, has so far been found living only in the waters of the Strait of Messina, Eastern Sicily and of Tuscany (Tyrrhenian Sea) (SCUDERI & REITANO, 2012; COSENTINO & GIACOBBE, 2015; see also SCUDERI & RUSSO, 2003 as *T. tingitana* Gofas, 1982; BOGI & CAMPANI, 2007; VAZZANA, 2010; SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI, 2011; VILLARI & SCUDERI, 2017; BOYER & RENDA, 2018). For a detailed description and a comparison with similar species, we refer to the original description (BOGI & CAMPANI, 2007) and the more

* Largo Giuseppe Veratti 37/D, 00146 Roma, Italy; e-mail: bruno_amati@yahoo.it

** Dipartimento di Biologia e Biotecnologie 'Charles Darwin', Sapienza Università di Roma, Viale dell'Università 32, I-00185 Roma, Italy; e-mail: marco.oliverio@uniroma1.it

Figure 1. *Tricolia* spp. from Los Escullos (Spain), 4-6 m depth. A-E: *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2017,) height 1.95 mm; F, G: *Tricolia landinii* juvenile, height 1.5 mm; H, I: *Tricolia miniata* (Monterosato, 1884), height 2.1 and 1.5 mm.

Figura 1. *Tricolia* spp. de Los Escullos (España), 4-6 m de profundidad. A-E: *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2017, altura 1,95 mm; F, G: *Tricolia landinii* juvenil, altura 1,5 mm; H, I: *Tricolia miniata* (Monterosato, 1884), altura 2,1 y 1,5 mm.

Table I. Measurements of teleoconch and protoconch of *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2007 (Fig. 1A-G) and *Tricolia miniata* (Monterosato, 1884) (Fig. 1H, I) in mm, from Los Escullos, Almeria (Spain).

Table I. Medidas de la teleoconcha y protoconcha de *Tricolia landinii* Bogi & Campani, 2007 (Fig. 1A-G) y *Tricolia miniata* (Monterosato, 1884) (Fig. 1H, I) en mm, de Los Escullos, Almeria (Spain).

<i>Tricolia landinii</i>	Fig. 1A-E	Fig. 1F-G	<i>Tricolia miniata</i>	Fig. 1H	Fig. 1I
Teleoconch			Teleoconch		
Height	1.95	1.5	Height	2.1	1.5
Width	1.75	1.45	Width	1.77	1.4
Number of whorls	2.5	2.1	Number of whorls	2.8	2.1
Aperture height	1.35	1.05	Aperture height	1.2	1.0
Last whorl height	1.77	1.3	Last whorl height	1.75	1.35
Height/width ratio	1.11	1.03	Height/width ratio	1.18	1.07
Height/last whorl ratio	1.09	1.15	Height/last whorl ratio	1.2	1.11
Height/aperture ratio	1.44	1.43	Height/aperture ratio	1.75	1.5
Protoconch			Protoconch		
Maximum diameter	0.200	0.200	Maximum diameter	0.225	0.287

recent integrative description (SCUDERI & REITANO, 2012).

In a sample of bioclastic sediment collected at Los Escullos, Almeria (Spain), in 4-6 m depth, specimens of four species of the genus *Tricolia* were found: *T. pullus*, *T. speciosa*, *T. miniata* and *T. landinii*. The material of the latter species consisted of 5 shells, four juveniles and one adult (Figs. 1A-G) in different states of preservation.

DESCRIPTION OF THE LARGEST FIGURED SPECIMEN (FIG. 1A-E)

Shell globular with wide aperture, of 2.5 convex whorls, without medial compression. Height 1.95 mm, width 1.75 mm, height of the last whorl 1.77 mm, aperture height 1.35 mm, height/width ratio 1.11, height/last whorl ratio 1.09, height/aperture ratio 1.44 (Table I). Protoconch of c. one whorl, flat, not immersed, maximum diameter 0.200 mm, whitish in colour. First teleoconch whorl dark brown monochrome; remaining whorls yellowish-white background with reddish-brown lightning-like axial stripes; peri-umbilical area whitish. Teleoconch almost smooth,

with prosocline growth lines. Umbilical chink with modest keel.

The smallest specimen (Fig. 1F-G) (height 1.5 mm), concordant with the holotype (height 1.1 mm), shows alternating white and brown subsutural spots, the peri-umbilical area brown and a narrower umbilical chink, without keel.

REMARKS

Tricolia miniata (Fig. 1H-I) differs from *T. landinii* in several shell features: by having the columella regularly arcuate (vs more sharply arcuate with an angle in the first third in *T. landinii*); in its larger protoconch (maximum diameter of the specimens figured: 0.225-0.287 mm vs 0.200 with smaller nucleus slightly immersed in *T. landinii*); in its more convex whorls with subsutural shoulder (vs shoulderless whorls in *T. landinii*); in its higher spire (with the first whorls more protruding, vs almost flattened in *T. landinii*); in its outer lip without sinuosity (vs evident triple sinuosity in *T. landinii*); in the lack of any umbilical chink in the adults, occasionally very narrow in young spec-

imens, c. 1-1.5 mm high (vs present in adult with a modest keel, but almost always absent in young specimens in *T. landinii*); in the dense spiral micro sculpture on the first teleoconch whorls (absent in *T. landinii*). The coloration is

variable in both species, *T. miniata* being probably more variable but without a clearly diagnostic pattern, whereas *T. landinii* has a consistently whitish protoconch and a dark brown first teleoconch whorl.

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